

**МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ:
ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА**

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**STIMULATING RESEARCH ACTIVITIES IN IMPROVING THE
RESEARCH SKILLS OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS**

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Annotation. Future primary school teachers in the article. In the conditions of modernizing education, the educational activity of students is becoming research. Therefore, it is of particular importance to introduce scientific research and experimental-constructive activities of students into the educational process.

Key words: motivation, independent education, scientific research, creativity, ability, evaluation, critical thinking, pedagogical and psychological knowledge, information supply

Stimulation of students' research activities is determined by the objective needs and interests of society, in the preparation of specialists for production and for science - this is its first and most general example. The social conditioning of this process is manifested in the goals, tasks, content, means of stimulating students' research activities, conditions that determine its effectiveness.

Regarding the importance of pre-reflection of reality in the development of character and personality, we can say that the effectiveness of stimulating research activities of students depends to some extent on how much they understand the need to study. In this type of activity and connect their point of view. This is another regularity of the process of encouraging students' research activities. Any human activity, its goals, methods, results are pre-programmed in his mind, which guides and motivates this activity. Seeing your prospects, experiencing the joy of success, evoking positive emotions, stimulating inner activity and personal development. It is for this reason that encouraging research activities involves creating favorable conditions for students' visions of growth prospects and understanding the joy of success in achieving them. Every university teacher understands well that the promotion of students' research activities is based, first of all, on the results of the diagnosis of the general education and development of students, their readiness and ability for such studies. So, there is a reason to talk not only about the results of involving students in research activities depending on how much they were engaged in the past period (school, high school), but also about another law - dependence.

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According to the results of the university, students are involved in scientific and research work at the university.

In turn, the analysis of university teaching practice, one's work experience at the university, provides the developing and problematic nature of education, and allows to focus on the conditionality of the success of the formation of research skills in students. Practice is convincing: the more fully and better students are involved in research activities, the higher its effectiveness. On the contrary, in the wrong organization of the activity, when the student becomes a passive performer or an indifferent participant, he develops the corresponding qualities, because inactivity is also a kind of activity.

Analyzing the participation of students of different universities in research activity allows to distinguish one of its laws - dependence on the professional direction of research activity. When choosing and defining research topics and problems by students, special attention should be paid to their relevance in terms of their usefulness for the future professional activity of students. The effectiveness of stimulating research activities of primary school teachers largely depends on the methods of its organization. It is not difficult to find a direct correlation between them and student success. Thus, we can talk about such a pattern as the dependence of the results of stimulating research scientific projects of future primary school teachers on the means and methods of its organization.

Research activities of students are mainly determined by their personal activities. —So, if in the process of research in a professional direction, a student acts as his subject and shows a certain level of activity, this leads to the formation of a permanent interest in both research activity and the chosen profession.

A lot depends on the right relationship between the students and the teachers in encouraging the research activities of the students. Communication with university teachers, students' research supervisors is the most important tool and motivational tool for students' research activities, so the wider and reasonable it is, the more students are interested in research activities. This is also one of the models for encouraging students' research activities. Taking into account this regularity, it is important to create an environment of humanistic interaction between the subjects of scientific research in the construction of the educational process.

Research activity of students is a process of joint activity of two subjects in new, unknown search, during which cultural values are transmitted and the result is the formation of a worldview. At the same time, the task of the teacher is understood

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in the creation of a hypothetical projective model of the formation of a developing environment for students. It is the teacher who determines the forms and conditions of research activity, as a result of which internal motivation for any problem arising from the research, creative position of elementary school teachers appears.

Educational tools - reference and methodical materials, special equipment, visual aids, audio-visual aids. Today, special importance is attached to the use of Internet technologies, the study of dissertations on the recommendation of teachers (where there is such an opportunity).

The main and most effective organizational forms of scientific-research work are: research departments or dissertations of a completely research nature; individual research work of students, that is, participation of students in the development of a specific problem under the guidance of a certain leader from the teaching staff; preparing a scientific report on the given topic; student clubs; participation of students in scientific organizational-public and competitive events at various levels (faculty, institute, city, republic, etc.).

The effectiveness of students' research activities directly depends on the implementation of organizational-pedagogical conditions and tools, including: the continuity and integration of pedagogical actions of the school and university in the organization of research activities, ensuring the students' research activities in a local normative, organizational and methodological manner.

We have presented those that have a significant impact on the effectiveness of the organization of research activities of students. The established patterns allow you to identify the Principles as the main ideas that represent the requirements for motivating this activity.

Since the principles regulate the resolution of certain pedagogical contradictions, it is obvious that, first of all, as a factor of their professional development, primary school teachers should understand the need (value) for research activities and methodical and methodical preparation of students for research activities. In our opinion, the principles arising from these contradictions do not require separate arguments.

Indeed, is it possible to succeed in the organization of research activities if future elementary teachers do not know its value and necessity? Furthermore, we show that it has a direct effect on the level of engagement of students in their research activities. Thus, appropriate methodological preparation of students is necessary.

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